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23

DIFFERENT MODALITIES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF OCULAR SURFACE SQUAMOUS NEOPLASIA

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Abstract

Purpose: To study the different modalities in the management of Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia(OSSN).

Method: A prospective study of 30 cases of OSSN was undertaken. Based on patient factors and tumour size and characteristics, 20 patients underwent surgical excision with cryotherapy and 10 patients were managed conservatively with topical interferon therapy. Patients were followed up for a period of nine months.

Results: OSSN is more common in males (80%) with mean age of 55 years (range 30-76 years). Histopathology report of excision biopsy showed 6 benign dysplasia, 8 carcinomas in situ and 6 invasive squamous carcinomas. Postoperative topical interferon reduced the risk of recurrence. Of the patients who underwent interferon therapy, complete resolution was seen in 6 cases.

Conclusion: Management of OSSN requires adequate excision and regular follow up to monitor any recurrence. Although surgical excision is still the gold standard for OSSN treatment, topical interferon has revolutionised the management of OSSN. Pre and Post-operative adjunctive therapy should be considered to prevent recurrence.

Key words: ocular surface squamous neoplasia(OSSN), modality of management,

Introduction

Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia(OSSN) refers to the entire spectrum of dysplastic, pre invasive and malignant squamous lesions of the conjunctiva and cornea.

Term OSSN was coined by LEE and HIRST.

Third most common ocular tumor after melanoma and lymphoma. Males are more commonly affected than females.

Grades

- BENIGN DYSPLASIA
 - Papilloma
 - Pseudo-epithelioma to hyperplasia
 - Benign hereditary intra epithelial dyskeratosis
- PREINVASIVE OSSN
 - Conjunctival/ corneal carcinoma in situ
- INVASIVE OSSN
 - Squamous cell carcinoma
 - Mucoepidermoid carcinoma

Appearances may be seen

-Gelatinous mass with superficial vessels

-White leucoplakic plaque that covers the lesion

-Papillomatous lesion with corkscrew like surface bloodvessels

Material and Method:

A prospective study of 30 patients presenting to tertiary eye care centre who were clinically suspected to have Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia(OSSN) was undertaken. The study was carried for a period of 9 months. A detailed history including age, sex, occupation and HIV status of all patients was taken. Clinical features regarding the location of lesion, type of lesion, and involvement of cornea were evaluated.

Based on patient factors and tumor characteristics, 20 patients underwent surgical excision with cryotherapy and 10 patients were managed conservatively with topical interferon therapy. Topical interferon IFN α 2b therapy in the dose of 1 million IU/ml eyedrops 4 times a day was given. Both the group of patients were followed up monthly for a period of 9 months.

Surgical Management

Surgical excision with 4 mm surrounding margins I sexcised with a No touch technique. Conjunctival auto graft / amniotic membrane graft is secured over the bare area with sutures/ glue. Cryotherapy (freeze-thaw-refreeze) is used in conjunction with surgery.

Criteria for topical interferon therapy

- Compliant patients
- Extensive OSSN
- OSSN with margins not clearly visible
- Recurrent OSSN

Criteria for Surgical Excision

- Size of tumor
- Patients non affordability
- Patients with no facility of cold chain

Results

OSSN is more common in males(80%).With mean age of 55 years (range 30-76 years).our study 16.66% patients were HIV positive.

Histopathology report of excision biopsy showed 6 patients with benign dysplasia, 8 patients with carcinoma in situ and 6 patients with invasive squamous carcinoma

Patients who underwent interferon therapy, complete resolution was seen in 6 cases.

Remaining 4 patients eventually underwent surgical excision for apparent lack of response to inter-feron.

No patients in either groups showed recurrence during the study period.

Discussion

Surgical excision should be done with adequate margins(3-4 mm) and with a NO TOUCH TECH-NIQUE.

Direct manipulation of the tumour should be maintained to prevent tumour seeding.

Regular follow up is required to monitor any recurrence. Maintenance of cold chain for interferon is important.

Pre and post operative adjunctive therapy should be considered to prevent recurrence.

Conclusion:

Although surgical excision is still the gold standard for OSSN treatment, topical interferon has revolutionized the management of OSSN.

Both topical interferon and aggressive surgical excision appear to be effective for primary OSSN.

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Nil

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Fig 1 Male:42 % Female:58 %

Fig 2

DOUGHNUT CHART
Invasive carcinoma 30%
Carcinoma in situ 40%
Benign Dysplasia 30%
Surgical excision case:

Interferon therapy case:

Pre Therapy

6 weeks follow up